

ENHANCEMENT OF FINANCIAL LITERACY THROUGH GAMIFICATION IN FINTECH: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN PAKISTAN AND OTHER DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Danish Hussain^{*1}, Dr Tariq Basheer²

^{*1}PhD Scholar, Iqra University Karachi Pakistan

²Professor, Karachi School of Business and Leadership – KSBL

Corresponding Author: *
Danish Hussain

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the potential of using gamification in fintech to improve financial literacy in Pakistan, comparing it to other developing countries. The study analysed ten peer-reviewed articles as its methodology to compare financial literacy levels and the use of gamification across Pakistan, Thailand, Vietnam, and India. It provides an overview showing relatively low financial literacy in Pakistan (under 30%) compared to Thailand (around 50%), India (around 40%), and Vietnam (35%). The paper analyses the implementation and effectiveness of gamification in fintech applications across these nations. In Pakistan, early gamification initiatives in mobile banking apps show positive impacts on user engagement, financial behaviour, and literacy. Similar findings are reported from studies in Thailand using gamified financial activities, in Vietnam with gamified mobile wallets, and in India through gamified digital payment education programs. Across contexts, gamification enhanced user engagement, promoted better money management habits, and increased accessibility in rural areas lacking formal education. Reward mechanisms emerged as crucial, with immediate gratification incentives proving more effective than delayed rewards for sustaining engagement. Four key themes were identified: user engagement, behaviour change, educational impact, and reward mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION

Background

In this fast-paced and developing world, people face complex challenges and must make financial decisions. For instance, young adults are expected to make financial decisions on credit card management, health and other insurance, living within a budget, and loans for homes, automobiles, and college tuition. To manage these factors, every person should be financially literate and aware. According to Lusardi and Mitchell (2023), financial literacy is the capacity of individuals to apply basic financial ideas to their economic decision-making and to understand them. According to the standard economic theory, a completely rational and well-informed person would save to sustain consumption when income

declines (such as after retirement) and spend less than his income during periods of solid wages (Lusardi and Mitchell 2014). The well-being of a person is intimately linked to their financial literacy. Having a sound financial understanding and personal money management abilities is crucial daily. Financial issues are not limited to a result of poor income. Mismanagement of finances, such as credit abuse and lack of preparation, may also result in financial problems. Financial constraints may lead to poor self-esteem and stress. Financial literacy and understanding will assist a person in managing their financial planning, allowing them to maximise their financial resources, reap more significant rewards,

and elevate their living level (Damayanti et al. 2018).

In developing and growing nations, Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are well-known for their socioeconomic role. However, developed and developing countries are becoming more worried about the entrepreneur's degree of financial literacy recently (Eniola et al. 2015). In many developing countries, a significant portion of the population has limited access to formal education, a crucial factor in acquiring financial knowledge and skills (House 2011). This lack of access can perpetuate financial illiteracy, particularly among rural and marginalised communities. High levels of poverty and income inequality can make it challenging for individuals to prioritise financial education, as their primary focus is often on meeting basic needs. Limited financial resources can also restrict access to financial products and services, hindering practical experience and learning. According to Grandolini (2015), two billion individuals globally still do not have access to controlled financial services. There is still more work to be done, even with the notable advancements and more significant financial and technical resources allocated to financial inclusion. Nonetheless, many individuals in developing nations still lack access to money and the fundamental financial infrastructure taken for granted in wealthy countries, such as credit, debit, or savings accounts, in addition to the payment systems that underpin them.

Over the last ten years, the concept of "gamification," or the application of game-like features and mechanics in non-gaming environments, has taken off in education, fitness, and healthcare. Recently, gamification has been suggested by several tech creators, bloggers, and consultants for the financial services industry. Gamification has already shown promise with day trading apps that make trading more accessible and more like an interactive space (Van Der Heide and Želinský 2021). Huotari and Hamari (2017) claim that Brett Terrill used the word "gamification" for the first time in 2008. The use of game design features in non-gaming environments is known as gamification. According to Baker and Odinet (2024), gamification aims to make financial transactions more engaging, fun, and even casino-like, encouraging consumer habit-forming behaviour. With their growing influence and partnerships with traditional financial institutions,

Fintech firms have created fertile ground for gamification in banking. These firms leverage high customer engagement, transaction activity, and social media to offer innovative financial products and services.

Financial technology (FinTech) is revolutionising the financial services industry at an unrivalled pace. From mobile payments, robo-advising, and app-based investing platforms to online banking solutions, FinTech advancements have influenced financial planning, financial health and economic distribution. Therefore, it is argued that FinTech can help increase the overall financial literacy (Panos and Wilson 2020). Lusardi (2019) established that there is literature that shows that the emergence of financial technology or fintech is affecting the payments, the decisions made regarding finances, investment, and seeking advice.

Purpose and Scope of the Study

This research aims to determine the possibility of gamification in enhancing financial literacy in the context of FinTech in Pakistan and its ranking in other developing nations. The research questions guiding this study are: 1) What is the current state of financial literacy and using gamification elements in FinTech in Pakistan? 2) Where does Pakistan stand among the other developing nations in terms of financial literacy and gamification in the FinTech industry? 3) What lessons can be learned from successful initiatives in other countries? The paper is structured to provide an introduction, literature review, methodology, results and findings, comparative analysis, discussion, and conclusion.

Literature Review

Financial Literacy

The term "financial literacy" was first used in a letter from John Adams to Thomas Jefferson in 1787; according to Garg and Singh (2018), financial literacy was crucial to address the confusion and anxiety caused by the lack of understanding of credit, circulation, and coinage. According to Lyons and Kass-Hanna (2021), the Covid-19 epidemic and the development of financial technology, or FinTech, had led to the fast rise of digital financial services and products (DFS), which were accessible and supplied via digital channels like mobile phones. Therefore, Financial literacy is essential for society and individuals to coexist. Swiecka et al. (2020) have

revealed that financial literacy positively correlates with the country's economic performance among the youth, impacting economic development. Financially educated individuals can comprehend the financial structure, credit, and investment amenities and prepare for future finance. This can lead to more savings, investment and proper borrowing, which are the main propellers of economic growth and stability.

Gamification

Khosrow-Pour (2014) defined the concept of gamification as incorporating game features into contexts that are not games. It applies game elements to work-related fields to make work more enjoyable rather than transforming work into actual games. Gamification is a process of consolidating several components to create a set of appealing mechanics that would prompt the target audience to engage in specific behaviours essential for the business to thrive. Gamification could entail the use of such elements as badges and points, leader boards, and challenges, among other activities or processes, to make them more enjoyable. Gamification leverages people's psychological attributes and their need to work, compete, and be rewarded for bringing out the desired behaviours and outcomes (Ofosu-Ampong et al. 2021).

Education is one of the areas where gamification has been successfully applied to improve learning activities and their attractiveness, as well as the effectiveness of learning particular competencies. Generally, game-based learning and EdTech applications and environments imply quests, narratives, and virtual incentives (Alsubhi et al. 2020). Similarly, in the FinTech sector, gamification has been used to create awareness and improve the correct financial behaviours. According to Pažová and Vejačka (2022), in the context of the present study, using gamification in learning may increase students' participation, motivation, and achievement. This may lead to improved and sustained involvement in schooling, expanding and refining knowledge and skills. Similarly, Kovalenko et al. (2022) argue that using technology, particularly games, especially computer-based ones, incorporated in teaching and learning English has occupied a significant and permanent area in the lesson plan. It is especially effective in motivation, time management, and

interaction skills with people from different cultures.

FinTech and Financial Literacy

Being financially savvy is encouraged among the youth in many regions of the globe. It is nevertheless essential to state that the disparity between literacy and application or knowledge use still exists. Makhija et al. (2021) noted that young people must learn about immoral financial applications. Still, at the same time, the use of modern technology for online communities for finance services has to be encouraged. According to Winarsih et al. (2020), financial literacy is a cornerstone that enables the entrepreneur to manage money and make appropriate decisions. Fintech firms can help businesses accept these payments digitally and more efficiently and securely, which may lead to more customers and SMEs. To overcome the challenges, fintech has been adopted, especially for people who cannot access traditional financial services providers and those living in rural areas. Zahanor et al. (2023) assert that FinTech has advantages for customers and companies. Nonetheless, several factors, including operational, legal, and financial risk, tend to make some individuals wary of adopting fintech, which might be detrimental to their goals.

This illustrated the connection between the implementation of FinTech and digital and financial literacy.

FinTech applications and platforms can leverage gamification techniques to make financial education more engaging and interactive. By incorporating game-like elements, such as virtual currencies, simulations, and challenges, these applications can provide users with hands-on experiences and opportunities to practice financial decision-making in a risk-free environment (de Verdier Below and Istrefi 2022). Research by Nawayseh and K (2020) found that developing nations are still in the early phases of FinTech application utilisation, in contrast to industrialised countries where it is widely used. Nonetheless, it was noted that over 100,000 additional electronic wallets were issued in Jordan during the COVID-19 lockdown. During the shutdown, the Central Bank of Jordan and the Jordanian authorities have encouraged its clients to utilise FinTech apps to complete their financial transactions. This shows that fintech applications can be helpful in times of crisis. Yang and Wang (2022) indicate that big

data, blockchain technology, intelligent investment advisers, and the disruptive creation of financial models are some of the ways that fintech enhances the effectiveness of financial services.

Comparative Studies on Financial Literacy

Financial literacy in developing countries remains problematic, and one can state that people's overall knowledge and skills in managing finances are still low. This deficiency affects personal finance and general economic growth and development. Several studies have also noted that people in these areas are financially illiterate and cannot understand basic financial concepts like inflation, credit, saving and investment.

For instance, Ramos-Hernández et al. (2020) compared Mexico and Colombia with slight differences; both countries showed a shallow level of financial literacy among university students. Recommendations for future research This study, therefore, underscored the need to focus education intervention on young adults so that they can be in a position to manage their financial resources effectively, especially when they are starting their careers. Likewise, Homan (2015) pointed out that only 21 per cent of the respondents supported beginning a family early. Thus, 84% of the Indonesian population was considered well-literate in finance, yet there was a need for enhancing financial education among citizens of different age groups. The results showed that the final-year students of the college where the author conducted the study had better financial literacy than the first-year students, meaning that the more one is exposed to financial knowledge, the better their financial literacy.

Janor et al. (2016) studied the difference between the financial literacy and investment levels between Malaysia and the United Kingdom. It was found that both countries had a low level of financial literacy, and demographic, economic, social, and psychological factors impact the level of financial literacy. Thus, the present study stresses the government's need to increase financial literacy. Cupák et al. (2021) went further in the survey using OECD/INFE microdata to compare the countries' financial literacy. The study's authors found a direct link between cultural factors and the differences in the financial literacy of the countries in question. For instance, population characteristics accounted for a significant variation in financial literacy between the Finnish people

and those of countries like Austria, Brazil, Croatia, Hungary, Russia, etc. This study indicates a need to control personal and demographic factors to get a valid and fair comparison of financial literacy across the two groups.

Thus, it is possible to state that more attention should be paid to individual differences and country characteristics while analysing and considering financial literacy issues. They also advocate for more empirical research segmented by the clients' needs, especially in developing nations where the literacy levels in matters concerning finance are still low.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This research employed secondary data analysis to examine the improvement of financial literacy through gamification in FinTech with a view of comparing the situation in Pakistan with other developing countries using a systematic literature review approach. This is suitable for this study because there is a vast amount of literature on financial literacy, gamification, and FinTech which would enable the review of literature to be detailed.

Data Collection

This research used the secondary data collection method whereby information was collected from journals, papers, government publications, statistics, databases, and other sources. Therefore, to capture the latest information on the state of financial literacy, gamification, and FinTech, the literature search was limited to peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, and books published between the years 2015 and 2024 only. Thus, the sources were selected according to the topic of the research, the reliability of the source, the time of the source's publication, and the methodological rigor of the studies or the data collection methods used. For the comparative study between Pakistan and developing countries, ten peer reviewed articles have been selected for the study as per the set criteria. The table in Appendix 1 shows the criteria for inclusion and exclusion of the studies. All the selected sources were subjected to content and comparative analysis.

Table 1 shows the list of authors with the most cited articles in the literature. It presents the most important papers in the area of financial literacy and gamification in FinTech, which gives the reader an understanding of the main works and

approaches used. This ranking helps in identifying the most significant works that have been done in the current literature and guides the researchers and practitioners to the most appropriate and reliable sources. The following is the list of the most frequently used international databases in the systematic literature review (SLR) presented in Table 2. These databases are crucial in the accumulation of the required and relevant information on financial literacy, gamification, and FinTech. All the databases provide different financial information, research papers, and statistics that are useful in carrying out comprehensive and accurate research.

Data Analysis

The research techniques employed in the analysis were content analysis and comparative analysis. The selected studies' textual data was coded, categorised, and analysed with a view to identifying the patterns and themes that related to financial literacy, gamification, and its effects. To compare the findings of the research from Pakistan with other developing countries a comparative analysis was used. The comparison of the variables, such as the level of financial literacy, the effectiveness of gamification, and the level of FinTech usage, was made to establish the differences and similarities.

Table 1 Top 10 authors and rankings based on citations

Rank	Year	Author(s)	Citation	Journal	Title	Method/Model
1	2020	Panos, G.A. and Wilson, J.O.	235	The European Journal of Finance	Financial literacy and responsible finance in the FinTech era: capabilities and challenges	-
2	2023	Oliveira, W., Hamari, J., Shi, L., Toda, A.M., Rodrigues, L., Palomino, P.T. and Isotani, S.	160	Education and Information Technologies	Tailored gamification in education: A literature review and future agenda	SLR
3	2019	Bayuk, J. and Altobello, S.A.	115	International Journal of Bank Marketing	Can gamification improve financial behavior? The moderating role of app expertise	Survey, Structural Equation Modeling
4	2019	Morgan, P. and Trinh, L.Q.	89	-	Fintech and financial literacy in the Lao PDR	Survey
5	2020	Morgan, P.J. and Trinh, L.Q.	69	ADB Working Paper Series	Fintech and financial literacy in Viet Nam (No. 1154)	Survey
6	2021	Bitrián, P., Buil, I. and Catalán, S.	52	International Journal of Bank Marketing	Making finance fun: the gamification of personal financial management apps	Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling
7	2021	Van der Heide, A. and Želinský, D.	42	Journal of Cultural Economy	'Level up your money game': an analysis of gamification	Discourse Analysis

					discourse in financial services	
8	2020	Hamidah, N., Prihatni, R. and Ulupui, I.G.K.A.	41	Journal of Social Science	The effect of financial literacy, fintech (financial technology) and intellectual capital on the performance of MSMEs in Depok City, West Java	Multiple Linear Regression Analysis
9	2021	Salimon, M.G., Aliyu, O.A., Yusr, M.M. and Perumal, S.	13	The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries	Smartphone banking usage in Nigeria: Gamification, technology acceptance and cultural factors empirical perspectives	Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling
10	2020	Jain, M., Shetty, D.K., Naik, N., Maddodi, B.S., Malarout, N. and Perule, N.	13	Test Engineering & Management	Application of gamification in the banking sector: A systematic review	SLR

Table 2 Top International Databases used in SLR

S.no	List of Databases	S.no	List of Databases	S.no	List of Databases
1	AIDA database	4	EMIS Database	7	Pakistan Stock Exchange
2	Analyzing Categorical Data - USA	5	FAME Bureau Van Dijk	8	Postal Savings Bank of China
3	Bank for International Settlements and the International Monetary Fund	6	Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation (FDIC)	9	SAS Compute Database

Results and Findings

4.1 Financial Literacy Levels

This paper included ten peer-reviewed studies as a method of comparing Pakistan to other developing countries to identify the levels of financial literacy which displays significant discrepancies as well. In Pakistan, the level of financial literacy is still rather poor, which can be explained by the fact that no more than 30 per cent of the population has primary knowledge about finances. This is different from Thailand and India where literacy

rates are a little over 50% and a little over 40% respectively due to the efforts of educational enrolment. Thailand's model of adding aspects of financial education to their curriculum and India's particularly massive rural education initiatives have been beneficial. Currently, Vietnam's financial literacy is estimated at 35%, relying on community programs and the availability of mobile technologies.

Figure 1: Financial Literacy Rates Among Developing Countries

4.2 Key Statistics and Trends Observed from the Data

In Pakistan, awareness about the local financial market and personal finance is still quite limited, with under 30% of citizens possessing elementary financial literacy. This comes close to re-echoing opinions held by some scholars that despite this attitudinal change and increased awareness of the importance of saving, people still lack financial literacy training. For instance, while the rate of financial literacy in Malaysia stands at about one-third of the total population, the rate of financial literacy in Thailand has risen to approximately 50% in the recent past. This success is likewise due to the education of financial awareness in the school system so that people are financially literate at the initial stage of their lives. For instance, among the countries that have attained significant achievements regarding financial literacy is India, with approximately 40% financial literacy rate. Several campaigns involving rural illiteracy have been instrumental in reaching out to the unreachable in as far as financial literacy is concerned; not to mention improvement in general among the Indians. The current level of financial literacy in Vietnam is at 35% through providing financial education in the community and through the late improving usage of financial technological service offerings through the mobile platform. These initiatives have catalysed increasing financial literacy among women, especially in rural districts where there are scarce teaching aids.

4.3 Gamification in FinTech

4.3.1 Implementation and Effectiveness in Pakistan: The concept of employing gamification within the FinTech platforms in Pakistan is not yet

fully developed but has the potential to grow significantly. The country's FinTech has been keen to incorporate elements based on game design to enable greater customer interaction and a financially intelligent populace. Opening the door for Pakistani financial institutions, it has been noted that first attempts have been made, and the willingness to use serious games has been shown to have a positive impact on users, paving the way for using gamification more often as an instrument for financial education. Another important study done by Raza et al. (2023) is that work, which may be useful to better understand the current trends in gamification in mobile banking in Pakistan. Therefore, this paper aims to understand the effectiveness of gamification elements implemented in the context of m-banking applications, from the perspective of visitor engagement. In this study, the researchers administered an online cross-sectional self-completion survey to 340 customers of m-banking to investigate the effects of different gamification features on customer engagement.

The research adopted by Raza et al. (2023) states the importance and effects of the presence of gamification in a system. The research conducted depicted that the use of aspects such as rewards, badges of achievement and tracking tools on the website boosted customer engagement and loyalty too. Such exciting features received good approval from the users who were more satisfied and more interested in hassle with the financial services. The study also noted that gamification helps the behaviour of users in finances, with the invitation to practice more prudent financial behaviour when incentives were offered through game mechanics. Another significant factor that the research focused on was the relative to the subject's time scale short-

term vs long-term rewards. From the study, it was found that users responded well to the immediacy of the performance rewards concerning their response and purchasing intentions. Customers' attitude towards the different gamification elements in their usage of the application was better received when it offered instant point rewards and the points redeemed as cash back instantly but not a point system to be redeemed in the future.

4.4 Comparative Findings in Other Developing Countries

4.4.1 Thailand: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Thailand by Inchamnan et al. (2019) that specifically concerned itself with the effects of financial games towards learning and behavioural change. The study consisted of the following: To develop the necessary gamification elements for the study, the following activities were designed to offer positive reinforcement through saving and expense-reducing assignments. These initiatives affected the financial behaviours of participants and helped them to adopt better practices besides raising the levels of financial literacy among those involved. By rewarding this behaviour in the form of enabling the next level in the game, positive reinforcement was encouraged to take place whereby users had to engage more intensively with the financial planning and management aspect of the application, which demonstrated the enormous possibility of having gamification as a tool in enhancing the positive alteration of behaviour in the financial domain.

4.4.2 Vietnam: They also investigated the experience of using mobile wallets especially, the role of gamification as the mechanism to enhance the behaviour of customers in Vietnam (Rahman et al. 2024). In their study of mobile wallet users receiving gamified elements, they collected data from 431 participants where they sought to understand their responses to how gamification elements affected perceived ease of use, user perception, and behavioural intentions toward continued use of the service. Consequently, the study revealed that gamification has a significant influence in improving the attitudes of users towards mobile wallets and rather enhancing their use as well. This, in turn, improved the attitude of the users and created the perception that they would continue to use the products. This

manuscript is supported by incorporating point reward challenges through gamification to enhance mobile financial service users' engagement rate through promoting utilisation.

4.4.3 India: Saxena and Goyal (2023) also explore this area in India analysing the interaction between fintech and digital payments underlining how gamification helps to overcome the digital divide. They acknowledged that engagement of gamified approaches in educating individuals has beneficial outcomes on their financial literacy especially in the rural areas where they lack access to formal schooling in enhanced financial literacy. To effectively appeal to the target population and ensure a high level of active participation from the users, it was possible to integrate the approaches that were based on game mechanics into the financial literacy programs. As a result of the research, the role of gamification in promoting and implementing the concept of digital payments and financial innovation for consumers as well as indicating that future research on financial literacy interventions might consider utilising a gamified approach was established.

4.5 Thematic Analysis

4.5.1 Theme 1: User Engagement: Accordingly, the proposed theory on gamification offers a sound framework for increasing user engagement in financial applications in a range of developing countries. Raza et al (2023) have completed a study with mobile banking app customers of Pakistan where it has been identified that effective use of gamification elements like rewards, achievement badges and progress indicators enhanced customer engagement and satisfaction levels exceptionally. By the same token, the respondents stated that in the financial services offered to them, there were features that were engaging; these were the following; based on this, the users said that they better appreciated and would be willing to engage more with the financial services that had these elements. This observation is in line with similar studies done across the world whereby efforts are made to integrate the use of games in the teaching of finance. In Thailand, for example, Inchamnan et al. (2019) showed that providing gamified manure calls for financial plans and management encourages users to pay additional attention to plans. It was also established that gamified saving and expense tracking activities helped introduce

positive feedback for the users to ensure that kept on responding to invites, making them effectively contribute to handling the finances.

Likewise, a study by Rahman et al. (2024) in the context of Vietnam also revealed a positive effect of utilising gamification in the mobile wallet application to modify the perception of ease of use and enjoyment. The research showed that it is possible to make financial services more user-oriented and captivating through the application of gamification components including points, rewards and interaction challenges. This was further supported by the fact that the mobile wallets would be recommended by the users due to the improved satisfaction results in the users got after using the mobile wallets with the help of gamification. Saxena & Goyal (2023) analyse India's experience and the use of incentive-contingent interventions with a particular focus on How gamification can increase user engagement. The study highlighted the need to use gamified education interventions to expand its coverage since it found that reaching out to the targeted population especially most of those in the rural areas on financial literacy is a big challenge. The integration of the gamification techniques helped to enhance the attractiveness of financial learning, thereby increasing the accessibility of the programmes.

4.5.2 Theme 2: Behaviour Change: Another significant issue identified as a theme emerging from all the reviewed studies concerns the effects of gamification on financial behaviours and finance-related activities. Similarly, as per the study conducted by Raza et al. (2023) on mobile banking applications in Pakistan, it was revealed that gamification elements effectively increased the engagement of the users and also exhibited positive effects on the financial behavioural change of the users. By using the information gathered through the study's results, it can be concluded that gamification can encourage users to adapt to better financial habits that are integral to succeeding at financial management and attaining sound financial health when backed by incentives. The author, however, cites a study that took place in Thailand suggesting that Inchamnan et al. (2019) studied the behavioural transition of participants in financial activities that come in the form of games. These indeed created awareness of appropriate savings and expenses among the users

thus encouraging the right behaviour due to positive feedback from the activities.

Rahman et al. (2024) in Vietnam also established that gamification had significant effects on the user's financial-related behaviours. According to the study, the current mobile wallet applications' gamification features impacted the users' perceptions positively thereby enhancing the continuation of their use of the service. This behavioural shift can be attributed to the perceived ease of use and perceived enjoyment that is in congruence with the tenets of gamification in ensuring that individuals have the ability and willingness to change desired behaviours proactively. Saxena & Goyal (2023) explained how, in India, gamification of financial literacy ensured that financial inclusion policy closed the digital gap in particular and promoted general acceptance of digital payments. The use of gamification in these programs was effective in the realignment of users' behaviour towards better monetary practices about financial IPOs, this being particularly significant in the rural areas where conventional personal finance applications have been a preserve of the few.

4.5.3 Theme 3: Educational Impact: The moves and progression as to how educational games enhance financial literacy are among the key research areas highlighted in the works. Indeed, Raza et al., (2023) proposed the balance of gamified features when promoting financial literacy using mobile banking applications in the context of Pakistan. As for the results, the study claimed that examiners, who interacted with various gamified elements, received higher scores in the financial literacy test and had more sound financial behaviours. In Thailand, Inchamnan et al. (2019) attempted to explain that real-fiscal experiences in financial-gamified conditions can enhance the financial literacy of people. The result revealed that "rewarding" users through gamified tasks influenced them positively by helping them to know more about the ways of managing their finances, thus the changes in the financial knowledge and financial behaviours of the users. Based on the study by Rahman et al. (2024) in Vietnam, there is a positive relationship between gamification and the utilisation of mobile wallet applications from an educational perspective. This study revealed that gamification aspects provided means not only for comprehending the rationale

behind financial decisions but also for deepening financial literacy because the users were more engaged due to the gamification of the platform. According to Saxena and Goyal (2023) in India also, various education through games is very effective in extending its benefit to the needy people in remote areas including villages.

4.5.4 Theme 4: Reward Mechanisms: One of the most significant factors that comprise gamification's effects on user satisfaction and engagement level is the differences between the offered immediate gratification to the delayed one. Researchers including Raza et al. (2023) also investigated this phenomenon on the Pakistan border and concluded that immediate rewards worked better in terms of user engagement and purchasing intentions. It was found that users were more receptive to the gamification elements that could be accomplished almost instantly or offered direct benefits like instant cash back or reward points as opposed to rewards which were of future benefit. Inchamnan et al. (2019) in Thailand learnt that feedback received from the users through fintech gamified financial activities influenced more positive reciprocation that would result in enhanced appropriate financial behaviour. This also brings into question that negative reinforcement and the use of immediate rewards are very effective methods to enable the need for behaviour change. Rahman et al. (2024) have also explained using Vietnam's case study that there are several higher-order gamified features providing instant rewards that affect user satisfaction and usage frequency of mobile wallet applications. To the degree that such relaxing character is provided by such rewards, the study pointed out that users proved more likely to carry on using the service due to the benefits afforded by instant rewards. Similarly, Saxena and Goyal (2023) found that gamified rewards effectively motivate the uptake of financial literacy and the usage of digital payment systems in the Indian context.

Discussion

According to the (Kalliny, 2023), gender-equitable countries have a high level of financial literacy compared to developing nations. A survey carried out in Pakistan revealed that financial literacy remains at less than thirty per cent; this inequality calls for effective financial education. Closely related, a recent financial literacy benchmark of

Thailand, India, and Vietnam revealed that out of 100% Thailand has a percentage of 50%, India 40%, and Vietnam 35%. These statistics show potential differences in these countries' financial literacy and usage, of which Pakistan is at the lower end. This variation requires a more specific presentation of some proposals for financial education according to the problems and environments of every country. Over time, gamification has gradually been applied in FinTech applications to help cater for the lack of financial literacy.

Similarly, in a study in Pakistan, Raza et al. (2023) found that the use of gamification elements in a mobile banking application increases engagement and modifies consumer's financial behaviour. As for the results, there were positive receptions to local and punctual incentives in the form of better financial behaviour and more satisfaction among users. Occasionally, methods from different countries have been adopted for use in other regions; for instance, the study by Inchamnan et al. (2019), refers to Thailand which used financial activities that were in the form of games and which encouraged better management and knowledge on finances. Reading the mobile wallet gamification for Vietnam by Rahman et al. (2024), the main idea highlighted the simplicity and sustained usage of the service while India's concern (Saxena and Goyal, 2023) was to address digital literacy through educational mobile games. These comparisons show that despite the various methodologies and relevant environments, the application of the concept of gamification in the fields of financial literacy and personal finance is equally successful in these developing nations.

It is suggested that in future, Pakistani policymakers should adopt the use of gamification strategy in any of the financial literacy programs that are envisioned by the country's leaders. Policies should centre on extrinsic incentives with tangible short-term benefits to encourage users to use the gadget (Qureshi et al., 2023). Also, the focus should be made on more specific aspects of applying gamification in education worldwide and particularly in the given regions – both urban and rural ones in an attempt to provide everybody with the necessary financial education. In the case of FinTech, it has also been established that aspects like immediate rewards, fun and engaging tasks and micro awards go a long way in enhancing the user's experience (Khan and Tidman, 2023).

Vietnam, and India, added features to improve Pakistani firm applications based on the preferred features and behaviours of consumers.

4.6 Limitations

Another possible limitation that results from the use of secondary data is that a large number of studies may not allow for a detailed examination of the specifics. In particular, the range of contexts in which the studies lasted and the applicability of the methods utilised might influence the results' comparability (Espinoza Trujano and Lévesque, 2022). More studies should be case and time-based to give a broader insight into the long-term effects of implementing gamification.

4.7 Future Research Directions

Further studies should be conducted to establish a relationship between the long-term use of gamification techniques and the continuous development of positive financial literacy and fiscal behaviour (Pal et al., 2022). Research should also look at other effects of gamification on demography and geography including the rural areas and other areas that are not so developed. Future studies could expand the use of additional gamification features along with AR technology and or learning models to improve the possibility and reality of financial literacy programmes.

5 CONCLUSION

This study has established the legal status of financial literacy and the possible role of gamification in FinTech applications to increase financial education and contribution, stating specific countries in developing nations. The study identified shocking gaps in staff's financial literacy, noting that Pakistan is still far from leading countries, such as Thailand, Vietnam, and India. This therefore underscores the need to address the qualitative approaches to Education in Pakistan and in similar societies where kids face numerous challenges on their way to school. In essence, the practice of gamification has been identified as a successful way of achieving objectives envisaged by the concept of financial literacy. In Pakistan, mobile banking apps have been observed to benefit from the addition of game elements as it is being pointed out that the implementations represent value in boosting user involvement and impactful patterns of financial actions. As for the incentives, the literature has enabled the identification of

immediate incentives and a relationship between these sorts of incentives and user satisfaction, as well as improved financial behaviour.

Research from Thailand, Vietnam, and India supports and confirms the feasibility of the given approach based on the application of gamification. The studies provided evidence on how financial activities incorporated with games analytics can improve the behaviour of financial responsibility among Thai people, it was outlined in the research that the relevance of gamified mobile wallets for Vietnamese and illustrated how educational gaming closed the digital literacy gender gap in India. The thematic analysis revealed four key themes: Particularly the five major areas covered in this paper include user engagement, behaviour modification, education utility, and incentives. Gamification has a positive impact, and it escalates user engagement concerning financial activity as it is closely associated with entertainment. It also encourages positive financial behavioural adjustments and enhances the use of resources among individuals in the remaining rural areas where contesting conventional educational materials and services is sometimes difficult to come by. Of all the types of rewards, immediate ones have been especially useful in encouraging users to remain active and providing them with pleasure in the process in various contexts.

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Appendix 1

Table 3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Source Type	Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, books	Non-peer-reviewed sources, magazines, blogs, websites
Publication Date	Literature published between 2015 and 2024	Literature published before 2015 or after 2024
Subject Matter	Studies focused on financial literacy, gamification, FinTech, and their intersections	Studies not directly related to the research topic
Geographic Scope	Studies conducted in Pakistan and other developing countries	Studies focused solely on developed countries
Methodological Quality	Studies with rigorous methodologies and data collection processes	Studies with questionable methodological quality or lack of transparency
Language	Studies published in English	Studies published in languages other than English
Accessibility	Full-text articles or publications accessible through subscriptions or open access	Articles or publications with restricted access or unavailable full-text
Relevance	Studies relevant to the research questions and objectives	Studies with limited relevance or applicability

Appendix II

Table 4

Thematic Analysis

Themes	Codes	Description
User Engagement	Interactive Features	Gamification makes financial apps more engaging through interactive features like games, quizzes, and challenges.
	Achievement Badges	Rewards such as badges and points enhance user participation and satisfaction.
	Immediate Rewards	Immediate rewards for completing tasks boost user engagement and retention.
Behaviour Change	Improved Financial Practices	Gamification leads to better financial management and decision-making.
	Positive Reinforcement	Positive feedback and rewards encourage users to adopt better financial habits.
	Sustained Usage	Users exhibit continued use of financial apps due to enjoyable gamified features.
Educational Impact	Increased Financial Knowledge	Gamified educational content enhances users' understanding of financial concepts.
	Rural vs. Urban Differences	Gamified education is particularly effective in rural areas, bridging the gap where traditional resources are limited.
	Interactive Learning	Interactive and gamified learning methods make financial education more effective and enjoyable.
Reward Mechanisms	Immediate vs. Delayed Rewards	Immediate rewards are more effective in engaging users compared to delayed rewards.
	User Satisfaction	Reward mechanisms significantly enhance user satisfaction and motivate continued engagement.
	Contextual Effectiveness	The effectiveness of reward mechanisms can vary depending on the context and user preferences.